

ANN-based design of miniaturized circular dual-band 4×4 MIMO antenna for 28/38 GHz 5G mmWave applications

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Article Info

Article history:

Received May 11, 2024

Revised Jun 7, 2024

Accepted Jul 12, 2024

Keywords:

5G technologies

Antenna

Artificial neural network

Millimeter wave

Multiple input multiple output

ABSTRACT

This paper introduces an innovative approach to design an extremely compact circular dual-band antenna suitable for 28/38 GHz 5G mmWave communications. Leveraging artificial neural network (ANN) and specially, multilayer perceptron (MLP) architecture, the suggested antenna's dimensions, which allow it to resonate across both frequencies, are predicted. The proposed circular patch antenna, featuring strategically placed rectangular and circular slots in the patch and the ground plane, attains a remarkable frequency range of 3 and 2 GHz for the initial resonant frequency of 28 GHz and the subsequent resonant frequency of 38 GHz bands, respectively. With maximal gains of 4.5 and 7 dB at the corresponding resonance frequency, respectively, the antenna also exhibits high efficiency. Remarkably, the dimensions of the individual antenna element are compact, measuring $4 \times 6 \times 0.8 \text{ mm}^3$, showcasing a notable decrease in physical footprint. Furthermore, the single antenna seamlessly transforms into a 4×4 multiple input multiple output (MIMO) antenna occupying a total volume of $16 \times 16 \times 0.8 \text{ mm}^3$, showcasing superior isolation and good diversity performance. This research not only contributes significantly to advancing miniaturized dual-band antennas tailored for 5G mmWave applications but also underscores the effectiveness of ANN, particularly MLP architecture, in optimizing antenna designs. The proposed antenna, with its small form factor, stands out as a promising solution for new generation 5G communication systems.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The advent of fifth generation (5G) technology represents an important moment in the evolution of wireless communication systems, bringing in a future that promises surpassing data speeds, ultra-low latency, and connection that extends beyond network borders. This 5G of mobile networks is predicted to disrupt a variety of sectors by allowing disruptive applications ranging from augmented reality and self-driving cars to widespread machine-type communications [1]. Unlocking the full potential of 5G, however, requires the

resolution of several challenges, with the forefront of these efforts being dedicated to advancements in antenna design. The use of millimeter-wave (mmWave) frequencies, notably in the bands of 28 GHz and 38 GHz, is a critical feature of 5G technology. Because of its wide bandwidth, the mmWave spectrum is a major enabler for satisfying the ever-increasing needs for data transfer and connection [2]. Nonetheless, the use of high frequencies poses other issues, such as increased air absorption and sensitivity to obstacles. Despite these challenges, the compelling promise of delivering extraordinary data rates and minimal latency has fueled major research and development projects focused at applying the enormous potential of mmWave frequencies for 5G applications [3]–[5].

Recognizing the strategic importance of these frequencies, regulatory agencies like the federal communication commission (FCC) have specified pioneer bands for 5G wireless networks around 28 GHz and 38 GHz, including ranges like 26.5–29.5 GHz, 27.5–28.35 GHz, and 37–40 GHz. This allocation is consistent with the overall aim of providing operators with dependable connection that includes high bandwidth, increased data speeds, and low latency. Within the regulatory frameworks of both the FCC and the European Union (EU), various frequency bands have been allocated for the deployment of 5G networks, primarily falling within the ka-band spectrum (26–40 GHz). These bands include foundational ones such as the 26 GHz band (24.25–27.5 GHz), the 28 GHz band (27.5–28.35 GHz), and the 38 GHz band (37–40 GHz), as well as supplementary bands like the 24 GHz band (24.25–24.45 GHz, 24.75–25.25 GHz), the 29 GHz band (29.1–29.25 GHz), and the 32 GHz band (31.4–33.8 GHz) [6], [7]. The incorporation of the multiple input multiple output (MIMO) antenna system endowed with broadband characteristics stands as a pivotal component in creating the communication architecture of 5G wireless networks [8]. This technological facet plays a crucial role in elevating data rates, enhancing spectrum efficiency, and augmenting channel capacity. Leveraging the intricacies of the multipath channel, this MIMO antenna configuration achieves these advancements without necessitating an escalation in antenna feeding power. This underscores the indispensability of MIMO antennas in the architecture of 5G networks, providing a pathway to achieve higher data rates while concurrently optimizing spectral resources and channel capacity [9]. A variety of literature study has dug into the examination of MIMO antennas working at 28/38 GHz, highlighting their critical significance in 5G mmWave communication. A notable example is shown in Rafique *et al.* [10], where researchers propose a unique planar MIMO antenna array with an inset fed layout precisely built for 5G applications at 28 GHz and 38 GHz. It is notable for its small size, measuring $41.5 \times 10 \times 0.8 \text{ mm}^3$, and it has excellent bandwidths of 1.39 GHz and 3.33 GHz for the corresponding bands of frequency. The maximum gain is 5.7 dB. Marzouk *et al.* [11], a MIMO antenna array comprising four elements and occupying an area of $110 \times 55 \text{ mm}^2$ was created. The attainment of a dual-band response was realized through utilizing slots shaped like inverted I's was integrated in the primary patch. It's demonstrates commendable port isolation and achieves maximum gains of 7.95 dB and 8.27 dB in the respective frequency bands. Raheel *et al.* [12], a 4×4 MIMO antenna is introduced for 5G applications. The system, operational at both 28 GHz and 38 GHz frequencies, showcases an impressive minimum port isolation of 28 dB. The observed gains are 7.1 dB and 7.9 dB at 28 GHz and 38 GHz, respectively. Farahat and Hussein [13] introduces a MIMO antenna designed by the author with a dimension of $79.4 \times 9.65 \text{ mm}^2$. It achieves a notable maximum gain of 9 dB and exhibits bandwidths of 3.42 GHz and 1.45 GHz for the respective frequency bands. Usman *et al.* [14], a small dual-port individual-element MIMO antenna functioning at a frequency of 28 GHz is introduced. The antenna features a total size of $33 \times 27.5 \times 0.76 \text{ mm}^3$, exhibiting a bandwidth of 0.4 GHz and achieving a peak gain of 6.9 dB at 28 GHz. The design approach utilized in the references mentioned adheres to conventional methods, featuring a thorough parametric study as a fundamental aspect of the design process. It is important to acknowledge that this traditional method, while comprehensive, may demand more time and effort. An alternative to this approach involves leveraging artificial intelligence methods, such as ANN [15]–[17], radial basis function neural networks (RBFNN) [18]–[20], and adaptive neuro-fuzzy inference systems (ANFIS) [21]. These intelligent methods offer the potential to streamline the design process and enhance efficiency by leveraging computational capabilities and learning algorithms.

This paper delves into the intricate realm of mmWave communication, focusing on crafting a 4×4 MIMO antenna array optimized specifically for the challenging 28 GHz and 38 GHz bands. Leveraging the power of artificial neural network techniques, our approach aims to tackle the complexities associated with antenna design in the mmWave spectrum, providing insights into the advancements crucial for harnessing the full potential of 5G mmWave technology.

This paper is structured to provide a thorough exploration of the suggested circular 4×4 MIMO antenna for 5G applications. Beginning with an introduction, section 2 delves into the design and performance of

the single antenna, offering a detailed discussion of the methodology and results. Section 3 focuses on presenting the collective performance attributes of the MIMO antenna. In section 4, a comparative study with other relevant works is conducted, highlighting the uniqueness and superiority of the proposed design. The paper concludes in the last section.

2. SUGGESTED SINGLE ANTENNA DESIGN AND METHOD

2.1. Layout of the proffered antenna

The proffered antenna's layout is displayed in Figures 1(a) and (b) for both top and back views. As can be seen in Figure 1(a), the antenna features a circular radiating patch with three inserted slots: two rectangular slots and one circular slot. The antenna operates using a 50Ω microstrip transmission line, integrating two gaps between the microstrip conductor and the radiating patch. It is crafted on a Rogers RT5880 substrate, known for its advantageous attributes such as a dielectric constant (ϵ_r) of 2.2, a minimal loss tangent of 0.0009, and a thickness of 0.8 mm. As illustrated in Figure 1(b), the back of the substrate has a ground plane made of metal, featuring an etched circular slot alongside the rectangular slot, providing structural stability. Remarkably, the antenna maintains compact dimensions of $W_{sub} \times L_{sub} \times 0.8 \text{ mm}^3$, with specific parameter values outlined in Table 1. Noteworthy is that the antenna's dimensions were optimized using an ANN structure, and subsequently, these dimensions were subjected to simulation using both the high-frequency structure simulator (HFSS) and computer simulation technology (CST) software for thorough analysis.

Figure 1. Structure of the highlighted dual-frequency antenna design: (a) top view (b) back view

Table 1. Antenna's physical dimensions

Parameter	Value (mm)	Parameter	Value (mm)
R_p	1.4872	H_{sub}	0.8
L_{sub}	6	L_{sg}	3.0862
W_{sub}	5	W_{sg}	0.4047
W_{feed}	0.23	x_0	0.2
L_{feed}	2.26	y_0	0.78
L_{s1}	1.4876	W_s	0.1986
L_{s2}	1.8876	R_s	0.7239

2.2. Proposed method

The inception of mathematical modeling for understanding the human brain traces back to 1943, marked by the pioneering contributions of W. M. Culloch and W. Pitts [22]. According to their model, the neural impulse arises from the elementary computation of individual neurons, while cognition emerges from the collective behavior of interconnected neural networks [23]. An ANN is a system of parts that are linked together, termed "neurons" in homage to its biological inspiration, where each neuron executes a basic function, and their cumulative interplay displays complicated global characteristics. Operating independently, each neuron contributes to a system with massive parallelism, data is stored within a dispersed fashion using synaptic coefficients or activation functions. Notably, ANNs possess the capacity to acquire knowledge from their surroundings, enhancing performance through a learning process. During this research, we focus on supervised learning, leveraging input-output data obtained from simulating 219 antennas. The architecture of a typical

ANN includes input, hidden, and output layers. The network's neurons in each layer are interconnected, facilitating the learning process. A multilayer perceptron (MLP) neural network, illustrated in Figure 2, involves input, hidden, and output layers with interconnected neurons. The dimensions of the antenna structure were optimized using an ANN structure, and the obtained dimensions were subsequently simulated using renowned electromagnetic simulators like HFSS and CST software for comprehensive analysis. Activation functions such as logsig, tansig, and purlin are utilized in the neural network layers, with the selection of the appropriate activation function warranting further study. During the learning phase, the primary objective is to ascertain a number of training procedures are used to determine the ideal synapses weights as well as biases. These algorithms encompass resilient backpropagation (RP), Polak-Ribiere conjugate gradient (CGP), Bayesian regularization (BR), conjugate gradient with Fletcher-Peeves (CGF), Levenberg-Marquardt (LM), scaled conjugate gradient (SCG), one-step secant (OSS) and Powell-Beale conjugate gradient (CGB). Their effectiveness is assessed to pinpoint the most suitable algorithm, aimed at reducing the discrepancy between desired and predicted outputs.

Figure 2. Structure of artificial neural network

2.3. Development and performance evaluation of the ANN model

In the endeavor to enhance the ANN architecture for forecasting the dimensions of the proposed dual-band antenna, an extensive dataset comprising 219 input/output pairs was meticulously compiled for training. The inputs were defined by the resonance frequencies f_1 and f_2 in conjunction with the substrate height (H_{sub}). The corresponding outputs encompassed the dimensions of key antenna components, including slot dimensions (R_s , L_{s1} , L_{s2} , W_s , L_{sg} , and W_{sg}), as well as the radius of the patch (R_p) as presented in Figure 3. The training process was focused on optimizing the network's configuration through systematic adjustments to the number of deep layers, the quantity of neurons within each layer, and the implementation of various training algorithms. This iterative approach aimed to automatically fine-tune the weights and biases, ensuring that the output of the ANN closely matched the dual-band antenna's required values and dimensions.

Figure 3. Architecture of the proffered MLP model

The performance of the model is meticulously assessed utilizing statistical metrics like mean absolute error (MAE), mean square error (MSE), and root mean squared error (RMSE). To pinpoint the utmost effective neural network algorithm and reduce the gap amongst target and predicted outcomes, the MLP network undergoes training with an array of algorithms, including RP, CGP, OSS, SCG, CGB, BR, CGF, and LM. Statistics criterion for every learning algorithm presented in Table 2, serve as a measure of the ANN structure's effectiveness. Notably, the BR training algorithm demonstrates the highest precision in aligning desired data and output

data, outperforming other alternatives. As a result of its superior performance, the BR training algorithm is selected for our study.

Table 2. Metric measurements used as statistical criterion for various training algorithms

Training algorithm	Training error			Testing error		
	<i>MSE</i>	<i>MAE</i>	<i>RMSE</i>	<i>MSE</i>	<i>MAE</i>	<i>RMSE</i>
LM	0.0084	0.0605	0.0919	0.0216	0.1206	0.1469
RP	0.0096	0.0696	0.0980	0.0124	0.0898	0.1113
OSS	0.0140	0.0824	0.1182	0.0177	0.0992	0.1329
CGB	0.0102	0.0720	0.1008	0.0128	0.0913	0.1131
SCG	0.0086	0.0676	0.0929	0.0109	0.0886	0.1044
CGF	0.0090	0.0632	0.0951	0.0115	0.0894	0.1073
CGP	0.0176	0.0846	0.1326	0.0094	0.0799	0.0968
BR	0.0030	0.0364	0.0552	0.0085	0.0690	0.0920

The same process used to identify the right training algorithm was used to determine the optimal transfer function for the ANN structure. According to the results in Table 3, the hyperbolic tangent sigmoid (*tansig*) is the best transfer function for training the MLP network in the hidden layer. The tangent sigmoid transfer function was chosen because of its ability to achieve a low error, as demonstrated by the findings.

The errors associated with varying the number of hidden layers are presented in Table 4, revealing that the best results are achieved with two hidden layers. Numerous experiments were conducted, exploring diverse quantities of neurons in the hidden layers to determine the optimal configuration for training the ANN model. Through these tests, it was observed that employing 30 neurons produced the most favorable outcomes, as evidenced in Table 5. Additionally, the diverse parameters selected for training our ANN structures are succinctly outlined in Table 6.

Table 3. Numeric representations of statistical criteria related to various transfer functions

Transfer function	Training error			Testing error		
	<i>MSE</i>	<i>MAE</i>	<i>RMSE</i>	<i>MSE</i>	<i>MAE</i>	<i>RMSE</i>
<i>Tansig</i>	0.0030	0.0364	0.0552	0.0085	0.0690	0.0920
<i>Satlin</i>	0.0076	0.0622	0.0873	0.0097	0.0813	0.0987
<i>Purelin</i>	0.0073	0.0488	0.0853	0.0101	0.0765	0.1006
<i>Hardlim</i>	0.0076	0.0605	0.0872	0.0081	0.0704	0.0899
<i>Logsig</i>	0.0065	0.0440	0.0805	0.0124	0.0840	0.1115

Table 4. Numeric values indicate the statistical standards across varied number of hidden layers

Number of hidden layers	Training error			Testing error		
	<i>MSE</i>	<i>MAE</i>	<i>RMSE</i>	<i>MSE</i>	<i>MAE</i>	<i>RMSE</i>
1	0.0056	0.0517	0.0750	0.0071	0.0670	0.0840
2	0.0030	0.0364	0.0552	0.0085	0.0690	0.0920
3	0.0706	0.2137	0.2658	0.0706	0.2277	0.2658
4	0.0706	0.2131	0.2656	0.0715	0.2293	0.2673
5	0.0705	0.2116	0.2656	0.0747	0.2350	0.2733

Table 5. Numeric values indicate statistical indicators across varying numbers of neurons in deep layers

Number of neurons	Training error			Testing error		
	<i>MSE</i>	<i>MAE</i>	<i>RMSE</i>	<i>MSE</i>	<i>MAE</i>	<i>RMSE</i>
5	0.0044	0.0463	0.0664	0.0122	0.0864	0.1107
10	0.0046	0.0366	0.0681	0.0137	0.0909	0.1172
15	0.0038	0.0348	0.0618	0.0205	0.0905	0.1431
20	0.0054	0.0333	0.0735	0.0208	0.0983	0.1441
25	0.0030	0.0347	0.0548	0.0161	0.0894	0.1269
30	0.0030	0.0364	0.0552	0.0085	0.0690	0.0920
35	0.0034	0.0379	0.0586	0.0111	0.0767	0.1055
40	0.0073	0.0408	0.0857	0.0100	0.0749	0.1002
50	0.0052	0.0359	0.0724	0.0075	0.0637	0.0866
60	0.0114	0.0738	0.1067	0.0093	0.0840	0.0963

Table 6. Final configuration of the MLP model

Parameter	Attributes
Number of samples	219
Training algorithm	BR
Transfer function	Tansig
Network structure	3-30-30-6

The yardstick for assessing the efficacy of the proffered ANN model is the regression coefficient, which elucidates the correlation among the forecasted values and the intended values. The outcomes for the proposed ANN model in this study are depicted in Figure 4. Across all datasets, the fit is notably satisfactory, with an R-value of 1. Concerning this coefficient, it is evident that the developed ANN model, structured as (3-30-30-6), demonstrates effectiveness in forecasting the values of the dimensions of the suggested antenna.

Figure 4. Regression coefficient of developed ANN model

2.4. Results and discussions

Using the developed ANN model, we forecast the dimensions of the antenna engineered for resonance at both 28 GHz and 38 GHz. The resultant outcomes are detailed in Table 7. This table presents the predicted values for key parameters such as R_p , R_s , L_{s1} , L_{s2} , W_s , L_{sg} , and W_{sg} , essential for the optimal performance of the proposed antenna.

Table 7. Predicted dimensions of the proposed antenna

Parameter	R_p	R_s	L_{s1}	L_{s2}	W_s	L_{sg}	W_{sg}
Value (mm)	1.4872	0.7239	1.4876	1.886	0.1986	3.0862	0.4047

The suggested antenna underwent simulation using both HFSS and CST simulators, employing dimensions predicted by the ANN model. A comprehensive analysis of various parameters was conducted to evaluate the antenna's performance. As stated in Figure 5(a), the reflection coefficient of the dual-band antenna

was determined through HFSS and CST software. The curves illustrate resonant frequencies at 28.2 GHz and 38 GHz for HFSS and 28 GHz and 38 GHz for CST, with reflection coefficients of -30 dB at the two resonance frequencies for HFSS and -45 dB and -48 dB, respectively, for CST. Notably, the antenna exhibits a significant bandwidth of 4.5 GHz for HFSS and 4 GHz for CST at the first resonance frequency, along with 2.4 GHz for both figures obtained from the two software. Figure 5(b) illustrates the voltage standing wave ratio (VSWR) of the suggested antenna. It is evident that the VSWR remains between 1 and 2 in both operational bands, indicating a well-matched antenna with the transmission line. Moreover, the results obtained from HFSS and CST simulations demonstrate consistency, with minor variations attributed to the distinct techniques employed by the two software platforms.

Figure 5. Electrical properties of the proffered antenna: (a) S_{11} and (b) VSWR

Figure 6 displays the electromagnetic radiation characteristics of the designed antenna layout. In Figures 6(a) and (b), the radiation patterns in the E-plane and H-plane are portrayed in two dimensions, corresponding to resonance frequencies of 28 GHz and 38 GHz. The proffered antenna showcases favorable radiation characteristics in both observation planes. Noteworthy is the fact that at 28 GHz, the antenna exhibits bidirectional and omnidirectional radiation patterns in the H and E planes, respectively. Similarly, at 38 GHz, the antenna demonstrates nearly omnidirectional radiation patterns in both planes. Figure 6(c) displays gain and radiation efficiency across varying frequencies. Notably, exceptional radiation properties are noticed across the full functional bandwidth, with the gain peaking at 4.8 dB and 6.75 dB in the respective frequency bands. Furthermore, the radiation efficiency exceeds 99% in both frequency bands.

Figure 6. Proposed antenna radiation characteristics: (a) radiation pattern at 28 GHz, (b) radiation pattern at 38 GHz, and (c) gain and efficiency over frequency

3. DESIGN OF THE PROFFERED MIMO ANTENNA

3.1. Suggested layout and S-parameters

Recognizing the crucial importance of MIMO antennas in exploiting the capabilities of 5G technology, particularly in boosting data rate reliability, this section is devoted to proposing an enhanced MIMO system that goes beyond the single antenna mentioned previously. As depicted in Figures 7(a) and (b), the MIMO configuration consists of four instances of the single antenna strategically arranged orthogonally on the substrate, resulting in a collective footprint measuring $L \times L \text{ mm}^2$ ($L=16 \text{ mm}$). This orthogonal placement introduces polarization diversity, thereby enhancing isolation. To further bolster the isolation amongst the elements of the MIMO antenna, an isolation structure, comprising four stubs with the same length of $L_1=6.5 \text{ mm}$ and cross-shaped stubs with a length of $L_2=5.5 \text{ mm}$, has been integrated into the top and back sides of the antenna. According to Figures 8(a) and (b), integrating the MIMO setup maintains the individual performance of each element without compromise. Each of the four elements demonstrates impressive performance concerning reflection coefficient and mutual coupling. The operational band covers a range from 25.2 GHz to 29.8 GHz in the initial frequency band, while the bandwidth expands from 36.2 GHz to 38.8 GHz in the second band. This arrangement achieves significant isolation, exceeding 23 dB and 30 dB in the first and higher bands, respectively.

Figure 7. Layout of the proffered MIMO antenna: (a) top view and (b) back view

Figure 8. S-parameter analysis of the proffered 4×4 MIMO antenna: (a) reflection coefficient and (b) transmission coefficient

3.2. Radiation pattern

Figure 9 illustrates the two-dimensional radiation properties of the proposed MIMO antenna across primary planes at frequencies of 28 GHz and 38 GHz. In Figure 9(a), the MIMO antenna displays a double-directional radiation pattern in both the E-plane and H-plane at 28 GHz. Conversely, Figure 9(b) indicates that at 38 GHz, the MIMO antenna emits a predominantly omnidirectional radiation pattern in both planes. This observation suggests that the antenna's radiation traits adapt with frequency, displaying directional tendencies at lower resonance frequencies and transitioning to more uniform radiation at higher resonance frequencies. Additionally, Figure 10 showcases the three-dimensional radiation pattern at 28 GHz in Figure 10(a) and 38 GHz in Figure 10(b), further highlighting the advantageous radiation characteristics of the MIMO antenna. Moreover, the proffered MIMO antenna demonstrates maximum gains of 6.84 dB and 7.33 dB at the respective resonance frequencies.

Figure 9. 2D radiation pattern observed at: (a) 28 GHz and (b) 38 GHz

Figure 10. 3D radiation pattern at: (a) 28 GHz and (b) 38 GHz

3.3. Diversity performance

To thoroughly evaluate the proffered MIMO antenna, an extensive examination of its diversity performance has been carried out, concentrating on vital parameters include the envelope correlation coefficient (ECC) and diversity gain (DG). The ECC acts as an indicator of the independence between the radiation patterns of two antennas, with a lower ECC indicating more distinguishable patterns. According to industry norms, an ECC of 0.5 is considered satisfactory. The ECC for a two-port MIMO antenna can be determined through two approaches: utilizing S-parameters and scrutinizing 3D radiation patterns. By leveraging S-parameters, the ECC is calculated using (1) [24], [25]. In Figure 11, the ECC values for the proposed 4×4 MIMO antenna are depicted, disclosing ECC values below 0.05 in both operational frequency bands.

$$ECC_{ij} = \frac{|S_{ii}^* S_{ij} + S_{ji}^* S_{jj}|^2}{(1 - (|S_{ii}|^2 + |S_{jj}|^2)) (- (|S_{jj}|^2 + |S_{ij}|^2))} \quad (1)$$

The evaluation of any MIMO system is based on the DG, a key indicator of the reliability and quality of a MIMO antenna in wireless systems. DG can be computed using ECC, as detailed in (2) [26]. Figure 11 illustrates that DG consistently hovers around 10 dB across the operational bands, confirming the antenna's strong performance in terms of diversity.

$$DG_{ij} = 10 \times \sqrt{1 - |ECC_{ij}|^2} \quad (2)$$

Figure 11. ECC and DG vs frequency of the proffered MIMO antenna

4. COMPARISON WITH SOME RELEVANT RESEARCH

Table 8 provides a comprehensive comparison of the proffered 4×4 MIMO antenna with other dual-band circular patch designs. Notably, the antenna in this study exhibits significant advancements. Its compact size of $16 \times 16 \times 0.8 \text{ mm}^3$ effectively addresses space constraints, marking a notable improvement over larger dimensions in previous designs. Operating at 28/38 GHz, the antenna achieves remarkable bandwidths of 4.5 GHz and 2.4 GHz, demonstrating superior frequency coverage compared to counterparts. With a maximum gain of 7.33 dB, the antenna excels in signal amplification, showcasing competitive performance in this aspect. Efficient isolation ($>23 \text{ dB}$ and $>30 \text{ dB}$ at respective bands) minimizes interference between elements, enhancing overall system reliability. Furthermore, the antenna's favorable ECC/DG values (<0.025 and >9.95) underscore its improved performance in terms of ECC and DG. This comprehensive analysis positions the proffered MIMO antenna as a significant advancement in the realm of dual-band circular patch designs, offering enhanced size efficiency, frequency coverage, and overall performance.

Table 8. Comparison of the performance of the proffered MIMO antenna to previous studies

Ref.	Size (mm^3)	Number of elements	Resonance frequency (GHz)	BW (GHz)	Max. Gain (dB)	Isolation (dB)	ECC/DG (dB)
[10]	$41.5 \times 10 \times 0.8$	4	28/38	1.39/3.33	5.7	$>25/25<$	$<0.001/>9.96$
[11]	$55 \times 110 \times 0.5$	4	28/38	1.06/1.43	8.2	$>26/28.32<$	$<0.001/NA$
[12]	$20 \times 24 \times 0.508$	4	28/38	1/1.2	7.9	$>25/26<$	$<0.001/NA$
[13]	$79.4 \times 9.65 \times 0.25$	4	28/38	3.42/1.45	9	$>30/30<$	$<0.0008/9.99$
[14]	$33 \times 27.5 \times 0.76$	2	28	0.4	6.9	>25	$0.001/9.99$
This work	$16 \times 16 \times 0.8$	4	28/38	4.5/2.4	7.33	$>23/30<$	$<0.025/9.95$

5. CONCLUSION

This paper presents an innovative dual-band 4×4 circular MIMO antenna explicitly designed for 5G applications. The design methodology is based on ANN to accurately predict the dimensions of the slots

inserted in the radiation patch of the proffered single antenna. Four duplicates of the individual antenna are then used to build the 4×4 MIMO configuration. The proffered antenna features not only a compact form factor, but also significant bandwidth in both frequency bands and high gain, making it a robust and competitive candidate for 5G applications, particularly for operation at 28/38 GHz. The integration of ANN into the design process not only speeds up the prediction of dimensions, but also highlights the paper's innovative methodology for optimizing the performance of MIMO antennas. This study represents a substantial contribution to the ongoing advancement of antenna technology for 5G communication systems, presenting a promising solution that seamlessly combines compact design, high bandwidth and increased gain for superior connectivity in the era of next-generation wireless networks.

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